

**Report on the results from the webinar on Webinar
on policy recommendations for the production and
use of EOMs**

D6.5 – Webinar on policy recommendations

Due date of deliverable: M46
Actual submission date: October 2024

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695

Project acronym: EOM4SOIL

Project title: External organic matters for climate mitigation and soil health

Project website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020

Project duration: 60 months

Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1

Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER:	Deliverable 6.5
DELIVERABLE TITLE:	Webinar on policy recommendation
DELIVERABLE TYPE:	Website
WORK PACKAGE N:	WP6
WORK PACKAGE TITLE:	Support and translate
DELIVERABLE LEADER:	CREA PB
AUTHORS:	Maria Valentina Lasorella, Irene Criscuoli, Ilaria Falconi, Gilberto Bragato, Claudio Mondini, Giovanni Dara Guccione
DISSEMINATION LEVEL:	PU

Executive summary

The project EOM4SOIL aims, amongst others, at proposing best management practices of organic matter (OM) for soil amendment and improving soil health.

Therefore, data refers to manure, compost, digestate and biochar and has the aim to evaluate the current European and national regulatory framework about organic matter production and use in soils and identify the regulatory obstacles that hamper the value chain development (both from the production and use perspectives)

During the final webinar for each EOM (biochar, digestate, manure, compost) have been investigating the production and use of different EOMs and the policy barriers hindering the production and the use of EOM' amendments and policy solutions to overcome the identified barriers.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

EU	European Union
GHGs	Green House Gasses
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
EOM	External Organic Matter
AECM	Agri-environment-climate Measure
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
AT	Agricultural transition
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
EC	European Commission
EIP-Agri	European Innovation Partnership - Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
EU	European Union
FSN	Food Security and Nutrition
GAEC	Good Agricultural and Environmental Condition
GPP	Green Public Procurement
IPARD	Instrument for pre-accession Assistance
MS	Member State
OG	Operational Group
PDO	Protected Designation of origin
PGI	Protected Geographical Indication
PPP	Polluter Pays Principle
SMR	Statutory Management Requirement
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
WFD	Water Framework Directive

1. Introduction on the objective of the webinar

The last national workshop with different stakeholders on EOMs policy recommendations was successfully held on-line on Friday 25th October 2024, from 10:00 AM to 1:00PM. The event was organized by the Council for Agricultural Research and Economics (CREA), in a joint effort between its Research Centre for Agricultural Policies and Bioeconomy (PB) and the Research Centre for Viticulture (CV). The event gathered over 160 participants from all regions across Italy; the participants included Managing Authorities (MA), government officials and scientists, as well as representatives from the private sector. The event represented a follow up to the “Focus groups on use and production of different EOMs as soil amendments” held in 2024. The event provided the opportunity to foster a dialogue among policy stakeholders, in particular MA, soil scientists and the private sector in a way to improve cooperation, to create and/or strengthened synergies, thus guiding the design and implementation of more effective soil policies towards a more sustainable use of soil resources in Italy. The present report certifies the achievement of the EOM4SOIL Deliverable 6.3 Webinar on policy recommendation on current national and EU policies related to External organic Matters’ (EOMs) amendments. More than 150 participants, participating on the webinar on policy recommendation on current national and EU policies related to External organic Matters’ (EOMs) amendments valued the opportunity to discuss methods and approaches for policy evaluation and to exchange national experiences

Audience: The target audience are farmers, national agencies and ministries, managing authorities, agronomist, scientists.

During the webinar each presenter investigates the way how existing national and regional policies support and incentivize a sustainable adoption of EOMs as amendment in agricultural soils, at EU and National level. During the presentation according to the description of the work of Task 6.2.1, the report, building on the results of WP1 (Tasks 1.1; 1.2 and 1.3) and WP5 (Task 5.1), brings out gaps or needs for revision/update of existing policies related to EOM production and uses to overcome existing barriers for the countries represented in the EOM4SOIL consortium. In addition, the results of Task 6.2 which have as objective to give information on best management use of EOMs, which has to be built on the outcomes of previous WPs, particularly WP1 (T1.4.), WP4 (T4.3. and T4.4.), WP5 (T5.1.), as well as on Task 6.1.

Furthermore, discussion have been made in view of the rules set by the new EU Regulation on the marketing of fertilizers (Reg. EU No. 2019/1009) and the expected implementing regulations and guidelines that shall accompany or follow its entry into force (July 2022). Moreover, in view of the achievement of the EU Green Deal targets, it will be useful to support the work of the EU Commission in drafting the report due in July 2026 (art. 49 of the Reg. 2019/1009) which shall take due account of technological progress and innovation as well as standardisation processes affecting production and use of fertilising products.

The firsts presentations investigate the policies addressing soil issues in the UE and task reference countries and policy gaps, solutions and recommendation to overcome existing

barriers that opposes to the production and use of EOM' amendments in EOM4SOIL partners' countries in particular for digestate, biochar and compost.

The webinar concludes with some considerations about the factors that contribute influencing the production and the use of EOM fertilizers among the EU countries represented in EOM4SOIL.

2. Introduction

The webinar on “policy recommendations for the production and use of EOMs” provided the opportunity to foster a dialogue among policy stakeholders, in particular MA, soil scientists and the private sector in a way to improve cooperation, to create and/or strengthened synergies, thus guiding the design and implementation of more effective soil policies towards a more sustainable use of soil resources in Italy. The present report certifies the achievement of the EOM4SOIL Deliverable 6.3 Webinar on policy recommendation on current national and EU policies related to External organic Matters’ (EOMs) amendments. More than 150 participants, participating on the webinar on policy recommendation on current national and EU policies related to External organic Matters’ (EOMs) amendments valued the opportunity to discuss methods and approaches for policy evaluation and to exchange national experiences

2.1 Opening session

The event was opened by Dr. Maria Valentina Lasorella, coordinator for PB of the activities of EOM4SOIL, of the EJP Soil project, who welcomed the participants and briefly explained the key rules and Teams functions to exploit, in a way to facilitate a proactive participation and a smooth interaction among the participants of the workshop. In addition, information about the European Joint Programme on Soil (EJP SOIL), a programme focused on Agricultural Soil Management addressing key societal challenges including climate change and future food supply. She explained that EJP Soil has the objective to promote a climate-smart sustainable agricultural soil management across Europe. In order to achieve this objective, the project involves 26 partners coming from 24 European countries. The project can count on a considerable amount of funds, which are the results of the co-financement provided by EU, various research institutions and the government of various Member States.

In addition, info about the results of focus groups carried out from March to September 2024 have been briefly describe results from questionnaire, investigating policy barriers hindering the production and the use of EOM’ amendments and policy solutions to overcome the identified barriers. The final objective of the questionnaire distributed to representatives of each country involved in EOM4SOIL was to collect info about the production, use and distribution of different EOMs at EU and MS level. The questionnaire is composed by a mix of open and closed questions, and it is divided into three sections. The first section provides a brief description of a candidate list of existing policies that are thought to influence the production and the use of candidate EOM’ amendments. Respondents are asked to prioritize policies from the candidate list in addressing/influencing the production and use of three candidate EOM’ amendments.

Mr. Francesco Ambrosini explained to participants how to access and use “Mentimeter”, one of the two online platforms used during the workshop with the aim to gathering, in real time, the feedback of the attendants on a series of issues proposed by the organizers. Mr. Ambrosini monitored the actual participation of the attendants along the various surveys proposed to

participants and elaborated, in real time, the outcomes of the consultations, thus allowing for a prompt discussion of these among the stakeholders.

2.2 EU policy instruments policy instruments increasing the SOM in soil (section one)

Thematic Analysis of the Webinar "EOM4SOIL: Policy Tools to Support the Production and Use of Agricultural Soil improvers"

This document summarizes the main themes and the most relevant information emerging from the webinar "EOM4SOIL: Policy Tools to Support the Production and Use of Agricultural Soil Improvers". The webinar focused on three key soil improvers: digestate, biochar and compost, analyzing national and European policies to support their development and implementation.

Temi Trasversali

- **Importanza degli Ammendanti Organici:** Il webinar ha sottolineato l'importanza degli ammendanti organici per la salute del suolo, la mitigazione del cambiamento climatico e la sostituzione del letame, la cui disponibilità è spesso limitata.
- **Sfide e Opportunità:** Sono state discusse le sfide e le opportunità legate alla produzione e all'utilizzo di questi ammendanti, come la necessità di migliorare la qualità del materiale in ingresso, la semplificazione normativa, la promozione della ricerca e l'incentivazione economica per gli agricoltori.
- **Cooperazione tra Attori:** È stata evidenziata la necessità di una cooperazione tra tutti gli attori della filiera, dagli agricoltori ai policy maker, per garantire lo sviluppo sostenibile del settore.

Transversal themes

- **Importance of Organic Amendments:** The webinar highlighted the importance of organic amendments for soil health, climate change mitigation and manure replacement, the availability of which is often limited.
- **Challenges and Opportunities:** The challenges and opportunities related to the production and use of these soil improvers were discussed, such as the need to improve the quality of the input material, regulatory simplification, promotion of research and economic incentives for farmers.
- **Cooperation between Actors:** The need for cooperation between all actors in the supply chain, from farmers to policy makers, was highlighted to ensure the sustainable development of the sector.

2.2.1 Digestate

- **Production and Obstacles:** In Italy, digestate production is concentrated in the North, with Lombardy leading the way. Key obstacles include regulatory framework, lack of comprehensive data and regionalization of production.

- **Nitrates Directive:** The Nitrates Directive represents a specific challenge, especially in vulnerable areas. It is proposed to update the rules and harmonize them with current climatic conditions, considering adequate spreading periods.
- **Innovative Solutions:** Among the proposed solutions we highlight the economic recognition of the ecosystem services provided by anaerobic digestion plants, the combination of different organic matrices and the use of innovative techniques such as precision agriculture 4.0.

2.2.2 Biochar

- **Features and Benefits:** Biochar is a highly porous material with high potential for carbon sequestration and water retention. Its effectiveness depends on the starting biomass and the production process.
- **Regulations:** Italian and European regulations present some differences, creating confusion among operators. A clarification is hoped for to facilitate the marketing of biochar.
- **Limited Market:** The Italian biochar market is still limited, with few producing companies and low demand. It is suggested to encourage the construction of small-scale or consortium plants and to promote the use of biochar in organic farming.

2.2.3 Compost

- **Benefits and Critical Issues:** Compost offers numerous benefits for the soil, but suffers from a negative perception by consumers, due in part to the poor quality of the product in the past.
- **Quality Improvement:** To overcome this mistrust, it is essential to improve the quality of the incoming material, promote the certification of the compost and develop stability indicators of the finished product.
- **Supporting Policies:** Supporting policies should include incentives for the purchase of quality compost, simplification of regulations, promotion of community composting and training of farmers on the use of compost.

2.3 Best practices for EOMs use in agriculture

Authors: Gilberto Bragato, Claudio Mondini, Eligio Malusà, Nicoletta Gronchi

The presentation described the EOMs available in the EU and their transformation processes to reduce volume and enhance soil amendment capacity. It focused on compost, digestate, and biochar, highlighting their benefits in improving soil structure, biodiversity, and ecosystem services. These materials have lower moisture and higher C and N content than manure, reducing transport and handling costs. For field application, full-field distribution before

sowing arable crops or in strips before the vegetative growth of permanent crops was recommended, with doses of 20-35 t/ha for compost, 20 t/ha for biochar, and variable doses for digestate based on the fertilization plan. The need for adapted manure spreaders or fertilizer spreaders was emphasized due to the lack of specific machinery. Challenges include the limited availability of biochar and the need for careful storage and application. Co-composting was suggested as a future step to enhance the effectiveness of these soil improvers.

2.4 Candidate list of EOMs amendments typologies

The candidate list of policies and EOM' amendments typologies are defined with the help of EOM4SOIL partners. In the deliverable D6.4 table 1 and 2 provides a description of a preselection of the policies that are thought to influence the production and use of EOM' amendments on the basis of which EOM4SOIL representative of each country are called to build the candidate list.

Information on strength, weakness, opportunities and threat for Biochar, Compost, and Digestate have been reported to investigate legislation and challenges on the use of Exogenous organic matter (EOM) used as soil amendments.

Biochar

- Biochar is a charcoal-like material produced from the pyrolysis or gasification of biomass.

Benefits of biochar:

- High carbon content, which can help mitigate climate change by increasing soil carbon stocks.
- Highly porous, which allows it to retain water and can be particularly beneficial in drought-prone areas.

Regulations:

- In Italy, biochar has been authorized as a soil amendment since 2015.
- It can be produced from agricultural and forestry biomass, excluding municipal waste and sewage sludge.

As of 2022, biochar can also be used in organic agriculture.

oThe European Union has also established regulations for biochar, which are voluntary for the internal market but mandatory for products bearing the CE mark.

Challenges:

- Production costs: High production costs and low market demand make biochar production economically unsustainable in Italy.
- Limited demand: The low demand for biochar in the agricultural and horticultural sectors is a major challenge.
- Lack of awareness: Many professionals and farmers are not aware of biochar and its potential benefits.

Compost

Compost is produced through the controlled aerobic decomposition of organic matter by microorganisms.

Benefits of compost:

- Improves soil structure and biodiversity.
- Contributes to ecosystem services like erosion control and carbon sequestration.
- Provides nutrients to plants.

● Regulations:

Compost production and use in Italy are regulated by the European Regulation on Fertilizing Products (2019) and national regulations like the Consolidated Environmental Act and Decree 75/2010. The Italian Compost Consortium provides a voluntary quality certification for compost.

Challenges:

- Quality concerns: The quality of compost can vary, and the presence of non-compostable materials like plastic can deter farmers from using it.
- Limited availability: Compost production facilities are not evenly distributed across Italy, with a higher concentration in the north.
- Negative perception: Some consumers perceive compost as harmful or low quality.
- Transportation costs: High transportation costs due to the distance between farms and composting facilities can be a barrier.

Digestate

Digestate is the material remaining after anaerobic digestion, a process where microorganisms break down organic matter in the absence of oxygen.

Benefits of digestate:

- Provides nutrients to plants, particularly nitrogen.
- Improves soil carbon sequestration.
- Can be used in organic agriculture when specific criteria regarding input materials are met.

Challenges:

Nutrient content: The high nitrogen content of digestate requires careful management to comply with nitrate directives.

- Limited impact on soil structure: Compared to compost, digestate has a less pronounced effect on improving soil structure.
- Regional availability: Similar to compost, digestate production is concentrated in certain regions of Italy.

Table 1 Outcomes ideas coming from mentimeter

	What should the future goal be?	What policy instruments would you propose?	What is the priority scientific information & knowledge required?
Climate Change Mitigation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon market; • integrate legislation to avoid soil consumption (e.g. law on nuclear waste that ends up on agricultural soils instead of in unused areas); • Need for operating systems; • Supporting C sink; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define more specific actions within RDPs measures; • Regulate sustainability; • certificate production processes; • The CAP is the main instrument of intervention for all strategies that may affect agricultural soils, on all the strategic objectives listed in this exc.se. • Awareness-raising. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More scientific data needed on the real impacts of CC on Italian agriculture; • development of indicators and clear relationships between agronomic practices and results on each specific objectives. • indicators
Climate Change Adaptation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is still too little awareness, in the productive sector, on the ecosystem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not compulsory measures but convince farmers of the value of their actions. Greater involvement of professional 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for greater integration among various existing projects, which are too fragmented.

	<p>functions of agricultural activity</p>	<p>organisations in active dissemination rather than administrative aspects.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • knowledge repositories and more exchange are needed; • Need for operating systems.
Ecosystem services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to define a dedicated legal framework on soil; • Finding ways to assess agricultural ecosystems services that have a direct value for soil protection and making them eligible for incentives under the CAP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foreseen the assessment of ecosystem services in spatial planning; • standardise activities in the various regions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indicators; • lack of a network of soil observers in the regions; • promote the use of standardised indicators common to the different policies (e.g. use the same tools when approving livestock farms , monitoring and evaluation of funds release);
Avoid soil and land degradation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foresee a law on land consumption; • integration with energy policies (considering land consumption from photovoltaic on the ground); • definition of specific (not 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote the Fast project as a tool for homogeneous management between regions and as a repository of applied knowledge; • national law on land consumption and control over; • mandatory measures to avoid land sealing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of a network of soil observers in the regions; • Monitoring; • soil degradation is also due to wrong fertilisation;

	<p>vague) measures;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve control on the ground by identifying critical situations; • favour the cultivation of permanent crops and improvement crops on hills. 		
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3. Policy Recommendations

The sources highlight several policy recommendations to overcome the challenges and promote the wider use of EOM:

- Incentivize EOM production: Provide financial support for building new biochar and compost facilities, particularly small-scale and community-based projects.
- Promote the use of EOM in Carbon Farming: Develop policies and methodologies to include biochar and compost in carbon farming practices.
- Increase awareness: Implement educational programs and outreach initiatives to inform farmers, consumers, and policymakers about the benefits and proper use of EOM.
- Improve data collection: Create a centralized database to track the production, quality, and use of EOM to support better policymaking and market development.
- Simplify and harmonize regulations: Streamline the regulations surrounding EOM production and use, ensuring consistency and clarity for producers and consumers.
- Support research and innovation: Invest in research to develop new technologies and applications for EOM, including the co-composting of biochar, compost, and digestate.

4. Conclusions

The webinar highlighted the great potential of organic soil improvers for more sustainable agriculture. However, to fully realize this potential, a joint commitment from all actors involved is needed, with policies aimed at overcoming the challenges and creating an environment conducive to the development of the sector.

Due to the increasing volume of organic wastes from urban, industrial and agricultural entities, the use of EOMs for as soil amendment is of extreme importance. Infact, the use and application of EOMs (e.g., animal manures, biochar, digestate, compost, etc..) is increasing worldwide, which can be used as a source of exogenous organic matter for soil. The soil application of EOMs as amendments has been proposed as an effective way of restoring degraded soils, while at the same time, protecting the environment as their use could be part of a strategy to eliminate massive amounts of sub products. This is particularly relevant in the current attempts to reach a fully circular economy, which advocates for capturing and reusing organic wastes.

5. Concluding remarks

Additional Notes for the implementation of the activity:

- **Dosages and Application:** The dosages indicated for soil improvers refer to the substance as it is and not to the dry substance. The application must be carried out in such a way as to comply with the Nitrates Directive and the specific needs of the crops.
- **Importance of Research:** Research and experimentation are essential to deepen knowledge on the properties and use of organic soil improvers, developing new technologies and innovative solutions.
- **International Cooperation:** Collaboration between different countries, at a European and international level, can encourage the exchange of knowledge and best practices for the production and use of organic soil improvers.

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